

1 **KRas mutant oncogene signaling activates the NLRC5 sensor.**

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6 NLRs are traditionally thought to and are defined by their ability to respond to ligands of specific structure.
7 We describe here induction of NLRC5 by the Kras oncogene in human cells. Interestingly, NLRC5 was
8 silenced following expression of oncogenic Kras G12V. Expression of wild-type KRas resulted in induction
9 of some level of DNA damage as assessed by induction of MSH2 and MSH6, XRCC6 (Ku70) and ERCC2
10 and ERCC3. Oncogenic Kras G12V resulted in induction of an alternative repair pathway evidenced by
11 activation of MSH3, XRCC1, ERCC1 and ERCC3. The NLRP1 sensor was activated in response to
12 oncogenic KRas G12V induction. Whether NLRC5 induction was in response to a DNA damage event that
13 precedes transformation, or a transcriptional suggestion of the onset of transformation is not yet
14 understood; additionally, whether alternative NLR activation by wild-type and oncogenic mutant Ras
15 variants reflect selective response and control of DNA damage and intimations of transformation-inducing
16 events, or whether this reflects non-specific NLR activation by nucleic acid damage-based triggers is not
17 yet understood.
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Results

We measured total transcription in human cells (epithelial cells of the lung) following ectopic expression of either wild-type KRas oncogenic or mutant variant KRas oncogene G12V.

Figure 1: Induction of NLRC5 by the Kras oncogene in human cells.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
84166	3.23E-08	0.1452	-5.5285991	-0.8024928	480.63	NLRC5	1117/19751	94.3

Figure 2: Oncogenic Kras mutant G12V silences NLRC5.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
84166	3.96E-02	0.182	2.057845	0.3748862	351.22	NLRC5	4008/19959	79.9

We observed strong activation of the NLR family sensor NLRC5 by the KRas oncogene (**Figure 1**). While NLRC5 was activated by wild-type, its expression was modestly silenced by mutant oncogenic variant KRas G12V (**Figure 2**).

Figure 3: Expression of wild-type KRas results in DNA damage.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
4436	5.64E-05	0.148	-4.0274112	-0.5960559	8719	MSH2	2538/	87.1
2956	4.87E-03	0.1068	-2.8155057	-0.3007519	13398.98	MSH6	5091/	74.2
2547	1.04E-02	0.1823	-2.5625432	-0.4670899	71686.27	XRCC6	5826/	70.5
2068	5.92E-04	0.1296	-3.4353583	-0.4453774	4561.33	ERCC2	3588/	81.8
2071	3.68E-05	0.1278	-4.1264335	-0.5274355	7182.79	ERCC3	2407/19751	87.8

Expression of KRas was associated with DNA damage. Damage of the DNA was appreciated by induction of mismatch repair machinery mutS homologs MSH2 and MSH6, Ku80 (XRCC6) and ERCC2/ERRC3 (Figure 3). It was not immediately clear to us whether NLRC5 was responding to DNA damage signaling or intimations of transformation; cells had not yet transformed (data not shown).

Figure 4: Expression of oncogenic Kras G12V also results in DNA damage, but realized and repaired through an alternative repair pathway.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
4437	2.47E-03	0.163	-3.027039	-0.4945946	4355.81	MSH3	1999/19959	90.0
7515	1.03E-01	0.139	-1.629469	-0.2265222	5072.89	XRCC1	5785/19959	71.0

KRas G12V DNA damage and DNA repair signaling was evidenced by activation of a different mutS homolog than was activated by wild-type KRas, MSH3, XRCC1, ERCC1 rather than ERCC2, as well as ERCC3.

Figure 5: The NLRP1 sensor is activated by KRas G12V.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
22861	1.50E-05	0.174	-4.329351	-0.7520202	5710.17	NLRP1	966/19959	95.2

Discussion

We described here induction of *NLRC5* by the Kras oncogene in human cells. A separate NLR, *NLRP1*, responded to Kras G12V. We are now currently studying NLR sensing of and/or NLR activation during transformation and changes in transformed status *in vivo* in humans with cancer.